

Getting too warm

Exploring effects of temperature upon aquatic ecosystems

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Front cover image: upper (major) image shows blooms of the toxic cyanobacteria *Microcystis* on Lake Erie (USA/Canada). A common harmful algal bloom species in lakes and reservoirs worldwide, this prolific organism can generate large biomass that can cause deoxygenation on decay, which can cause fish death (inset image).

Getting too warm: exploring effects of temperature upon aquatic ecosystems

QUICK START

The basics

- Temperature increases the rate of biological processes, photosynthesis, growth and predation, with rates roughly doubling every 10°C, but only within a narrow range (around 10-15°C) for a given species.
- All organisms have optimal temperature ranges; too low and some may become dormant; too high and death occurs.
- High temperature decreases oxygen solubility in water, while also promoting an organism to use more oxygen. Any excess oxygen production through photosynthesis, beyond the solubility limit for water at that temperature, is lost to the atmosphere.
- Combinations of high nutrient loads (promoting good microalgal growth), high temperature (increasing microalgal growth rates beyond control by zooplankton grazing, while decreasing oxygen solubility) and low wind (limiting the entry of oxygen into the water), can create conditions where the eventual decay of the biomass draws oxygen down to levels which are too low (hypoxic) for animals, causing death and further decay.
- Explore these interactions using a simulation model.

To run the model, if not yet installed, install Powersim 10 Studio Cockpit, load the model

- The *Powersim Studio 10 Cockpit* application works only on PCs operating *Microsoft Windows*.
- Visit the *Powersim Studio* download site at <https://powersim.com/download-cockpit/>
- Download *Cockpit* (64-bit or 32-bit; most PCs will be 64-bit).
- Follow instructions provided by *Powersim* to install the software. (Accept default suggestions)
- Download the model from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17521978>
- To run a model, locate the file in your *MS Windows* file directory using *Explorer*.
- The file should have the *Powersim Studio 10* logo associated with it - clicking on the file name will open the file within the application.
- The model will open into a Home page; **follow the onscreen instructions!**

Configure the model by moving the sliders on the *Configure* page (see figure, below)

- **Nutrient** – sets the initial amount of nitrogen nutrient in the system. The units are as mgN m⁻³; to convert to units as μM, divide this number by 14 (the molecular weight of N).
- **Wind** – this sets the wind speed. The units are as m s⁻¹.
- **Pulse** – sets the additional nutrient concentration added to the system to simulate a pollution event.
- **Pulse time** – sets the time of the pulse addition. The unit is day.
- **Temperature sliders (T@0d .. T@150d)** – these set the temperature at a given day. For example, to set the temperature on day 100 at 20°C, drag the slider for T@100d to 20. Temperature between the set points changes in a linear fashion.

Sliders controlling the microalgae (green) and zooplankton (red) arranged one above the other.

- **Optimum** – set the optimum temperature (°C) for growth.
- **Range** – set the temperature range between the lowest temperature for effective growth and the optimum as °C.
- **Sensitivity** – set the sensitivity of the temperature-growth relationship.
- **Umax** – set the maximum growth rate of the organism. The unit is d⁻¹; 0.693 d⁻¹ allows the organism biomass to double each day. The value is attainable at the optimal temperature and assumes sufficient nutrient (for microalgae) or food (for zooplankton).

Configure page, showing slides to control the simulation

Overview of direct and indirect interactions between temperature and plankton activity. Increased day light and more general increases in temperature with climate change leads to a temperature rise in the water (i). This temperature increase is enhanced under calm conditions (ii), while both warmer and calmer conditions also lead to a shallower mixed layer depth (MLD; iii). A shallow MLD keeps the photosynthetic microalgae nearer the light, promoting their growth (a deep MLD negatively affects microalgal growth; iv). Increased temperature, but not calm conditions, enhances gas exchange with the atmosphere (v), which operates to equilibrate the levels of oxygen (vi), while increased temperature itself decreases oxygen solubility (vii). Phototrophic growth is enhanced by day light and elevated temperature (viii), assuming sufficient nutrient is available. Elevated nutrient levels, especially associated with eutrophication, promote microalgal growth (ix), noting that nutrients are recycled from heterotrophic (including predator) activity. At extreme microalgal abundances, the resultant self-shading leads to surface accumulations of the biomass, darkening the water below while excess oxygen production is rapidly outgassed to the atmosphere. Phototrophic growth increases oxygen levels, but at night the heterotrophic (respiratory) activities of these organisms, as well as all other organisms, consume oxygen (x). The growth of phototrophs promotes the growth of heterotrophic organisms (xi); growth of the latter is also promoted by elevated temperatures (xii). Heterotrophs consume oxygen; if oxygen levels become sufficiently depressed, aerobic heterotrophic growth is negatively impacted (xiii) as the system becomes hypoxic.

Contents

QUICK START	2
Preface.....	6
Acknowledgement to Funders	6
A note to teachers.....	7
Age suitability and science language.....	7
Fit to curriculum	8
Scientific writing	8
Glossary.....	10
Introduction	14
CLASS ACTIVITY #1	14
Temperature and Life	15
Growth; resources and energy	15
Biochemistry.....	15
Enzymes.....	15
Enzymes and temperature	16
Organism growth and temperature	18
Efficiency, organism size and evolution to life at higher temperatures	20
Food webs and temperature	20
CLASS ACTIVITY #2	21
Oxygen solubility in water and temperature.....	21
CLASS ACTIVITY #3	24
Putting it all together – building a conceptual model.....	25
Operating the model	27
<i>Learning Outcomes</i> (introduction) page	27
Configure page	28
<i>Results</i> page.....	30
<i>Details</i> page	31
Conducting experiments	33
Setting hypotheses	33
Starting off.....	34
More complex experiments	34
Caveats	35
Excluded features	35
Adequacy of the description of included features	36
Conclusions.....	37

What you should have noted	38
Temperature effects – the basics.....	38
Learning outcomes from operating the model	38
Modifications to the model	39
Consolidation of what you have learnt and further aspects	40
CLASS ACTIVITY #4	40
Temperature effects – some more details.....	40
Types of organism activity	40
Optimal temperature for growth.....	40
Light-dark interactions	41
Temperature and oxygen	42
Water column stability.....	43
Water column stability and the balance of oxygen production and its use by microalgae.....	43
Nutrient availability; the role of eutrophication.....	43
Summary of temperature effects	44

Preface

This work is one of a series intended to assist in the teaching of ocean literacy and allied aspects of environmental education applied to freshwaters, such as lakes and reservoirs. It targets investigations on the effects of temperature on the functioning of the plankton that support the growth of most organisms in aquatic ecosystems.

The work requires the use of a simulation model. This model enables the students to experiment with a simple representation of the real world, to explore for themselves what the consequences are of changing temperatures.

The model operates within a **Microsoft Windows** application, called **Powersim Cockpit**, which is available for free.

To download this free application, visit this website:

<https://powersim.com/download-cockpit/>

WARNING: Only install Cockpit on a PC that does not contain another Powersim Studio product. Installing Powersim Cockpit if you already have Powersim Studio installed will overwrite Studio!

Acknowledgement to Funders

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Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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The simulation model associated with this work was developed using the software **Powersim Studio 10** (www.Powersim.com), in part by ARK dynamics Ltd. The model presented here is free for use under the Powersim Cockpit platform.

A note to teachers

Age suitability and science language

While this work may be used for independent learning, it may more usefully be used in support of class-based activities.

The information provided in this work is intended to support your teaching activities. You are best placed to decide how to make this information suitable, age-appropriate, for your students. Based on the experience of the author, the core concepts may be taught successfully to students as young as ca. 8 years, though the complexity of the subject can also be developed for ages through to university level. **In general, the recommended age is 13+, while much of the explanation concerning temperature effects on enzymes and biochemistry is more appropriate for 16+.**

Like all subjects, the topic of temperature effects on ecology, and plankton ecology, has its special words. While there are often analogous words that students will be aware of, and which you may use to help to convey a concept, it is very important **not to substitute the special words with others.**

A key word here is '*microalgae*'. While it may be tempting to refer to these organisms as 'microscopic plants', as do many teaching aids and articles in popular science, this is incorrect – they are not plants! Microalgae have evolved in a totally separate way from plants. Many microalgae are highly motile (they swim), and many also eat, sometimes using poisons, traps and even harpoon-like structures to capture their food. Some even steal body-parts from other organisms to help them photosynthesize!

Microalgae and plants do share a few things in common, however. Both are of global importance, forming populations so large that they can be seen from space, and they help the ecology of Earth to function properly. Both provide food for animals and other organisms. For their growth, both contain green and other coloured pigments that absorb energy from light to support the process of photosynthesis (fixation of carbon dioxide - CO₂), and they both need light, CO₂ and certain nutrients (e.g., ammonium, nitrate, phosphate) in order to grow.

This document introduces various topics associated with the effects of temperature variation on aquatic ecology, associated with climate change. This includes the subjects of deoxygenation and the linkage to eutrophication. These topics are explored through an investigation, intended to provoke student curiosity.

It is recommended that the subject of eutrophication is explored before undertaking the activities described here. The subject of eutrophication is considered in:

Flynn, K. J. (2024). Exploring eutrophication – polluting with too much of a good thing; a teaching guide. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12529789>

Fit to curriculum

The subject matter of this document may be aligned with various aspects of general teaching curricula. Some indications of this fit are considered here.

Topic	Language	Mathematics	Biology	Chemistry	Physics
a) Interpretation of written evidence	•		•	•	•
b) Written expression	•		•	•	•
c) Structured reporting	•		•	•	•
d) Interpretation of visual evidence and graphs	•	•	•	•	•
e) Calculations, equations, computer coding		•	•	•	•

A glossary of important terms is provided.

At the end of the document there is a section entitled ‘*What you should have noted*’, which will help students check their learning experience from operating the model.

Scientific writing

An important aspect of science is recording why something was studied, how it was studied, and what the results of the study tells us. To help in such recording, science writing typically follows a set of rules. These are described here.

- Scientific writing has a particular style, often written in the 3rd person (‘this was done’ etc.); use of the 1st person is generally not encouraged. Be aware that scientists make errors, and while they should not be biased, bias in their reporting (often in consequence of brevity, rather than being deliberate) is not uncommon. Science is regularly updated; this means that it is important to balance interpretations of dated literature (which may be more likely to identify ‘established knowledge’) against views expressed in recent literature (which may identify problems with established ‘facts’).
- What was done in a scientific study is described in the **past** tense; discussions are usually in the **present** tense.
- Science writing is non-emotive, succinct, balanced in description and interpretation. Correct use of technical terminology is important; this creates challenges when writing for a general audience (or, indeed, when teaching) when it can be all too easy to use inappropriate analogies. An example is to draw analogies between terrestrial plants and microalgae, labelling the latter as ‘microscopic plants’ – this is not correct and introduces a range of other comparisons and concepts that are not accurate (such as thinking that microalgae have roots, stems and leaves).
- Science reports follows a common structure. This usually comprises the following: **Title** (ideally, brief); **Abstract** (a 200-300 word summary of aims, objectives, results, conclusions); **Introduction** (the topic in general, and the specific aims of the work, often with explicit setting of hypotheses); **Methods and Materials** (reports all information required to repeat the work); **Results** (tables, graphs, photographs, drawings, with allied text to explain salient points); **Discussion** (considers the results, especially set against what others have said); **References** (literature referred to).

- e) Interpreting both time-graphs and x-y scatter plots are important skills for all students, not just for scientists. Photography and line-drawings are also important aspects of science; producing **infographics** is a particularly useful skill to communicate the findings to non-specialists.
- f) Various aspects of science require mathematic manipulations (e.g., unit conversions) and use of equations. Understanding and correctly using units, and interpretations of unit expression (e.g., mgN m^{-3} , $\text{gC (gC)}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$), is especially important. This includes on graph axis labels, and in the headings of table.

Glossary

Items in italics are defined elsewhere in the Glossary.

Abiotic – physical and chemical components of a system.

Ammonium – an important form of dissolved inorganic nitrogen (*DIN*) in water bodies. Typically used to refer to both ammonia (NH_3) and ammonium (NH_4^+); the latter form is more abundant in seawater.

Biological oxygen demand (BOD) – an index of the amount of dissolved and particulate organic material in the ecosystem whose consumption would also consume oxygen (O_2). Technically BOD is the amount of oxygen required by aerobic microbes to consume the organic material in the water. Usually tested in cultures grown over a set period of time at a set temperature. However, this disregards other routes of O_2 consumption (e.g. respiration by other organisms), balanced against routes of O_2 entry.

Biomass – the collective mass of organisms, usually given in terms of carbon or nitrogen, as C-biomass or N-biomass.

Biotic – biological components of a system.

Chlorophyll – the most important pigment associated with photosynthesis. Although often used as a measure of the biomass of photosynthetic organisms, the ratio of chlorophyll to carbon biomass (Chl:C) ratio can vary by a factor of 5.

Competitive advantage – advantage that one species has over another in competition for a common limiting resource (such as light or food), or against a common loss factor (such as predation).

Consumer – an organism that consumes biomass (as living organisms or debris that is particulate organic matter) and/or dissolved organic nutrients (such as sugars and amino acids, see *DOM*). Consumer activity results in the net decrease in the abundance of organic material in an ecosystem, and typically in the consumption of oxygen. Consumers are *heterotrophs*.

Cyanobacteria – a type of *microalgae* that are photosynthetic bacteria (i.e., prokaryote). Also often called ‘blue-green algae’.

Dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN) – a sum of ammonium, nitrate and nitrite; these are nutrients used by microalgae.

Dissolved organic matter (DOM) – sugars, amino acids, fatty acids etc.; any organic material dissolved in the water, but typically referring to products leaked into the water by microalgae or during prey digestion by consumers, or from terrestrial sources, such as silage. Consumption by bacteria is the main contributor to biological oxygen debt (*BOD*).

Dynamic – changing with time.

Enzyme – a biological catalyst, a compound (usually a protein, though there are important non-protein enzymes) that speeds up reactions that both create molecules or degrade them.

Eutrophication – an ecosystem status that is sufficiently nutrient rich that its behaviour displays damaging characteristics, such as excessive biomass accumulations which may cause deoxygenation leading to *hypoxia*.

Food chain/web – a linked series of inter-relating organisms through which energy and resources (e.g., carbon (C), nitrogen (N), and phosphorus (P)) pass from producer to a series of consumers, with the latter regenerating (releasing) the inorganic nutrients used by the former. A chain refers to a simple linkage, while a web (which is the common format in nature) refers to complex interconnectivities.

Heterotroph – an organism that consumes organics, often with the consumption of oxygen. Predators, such as zooplankton, are heterotrophs, as are bacteria. In darkness, photosynthetic organisms temporarily become heterotrophic, consuming sugars that they made and accumulated during the previous light period using photosynthesis.

Hypoxia – a level of oxygen concentration that is sufficiently low that highly active animals can no longer survive without showing stress.

Microalgae – any microscopic, unicellular, organism that performs *photosynthesis* (able to perform phototrophy). These include *cyanobacteria* and *protists*. Not all microalgae are planktonic. Almost certainly all microalgae can consume organic nutrients (thus they are able to perform *osmotrophy*); some can grow in total darkness using such nutrients.

Mixed layer – a zone in the water column which is, relative to adjoining zones, well mixed. Typically refers to the upper 10s -100s m of the water column, stirred by atmospheric processes.

Mixed layer depth (MLD) – the depth of the mixed layer, between the water-air interface and the *pycnocline* (typically, *thermocline*).

Mixoplankton – a type of a *protist microalgae* that use *photosynthesis*, *osmotrophy* and can also eat. Many so-called *phytoplankton* are actually mixoplankton, consuming prey through a process generally termed as phagotrophy (engulfment).

Model – a simplification of reality.

Nitrate – the most abundant form of dissolved inorganic nitrogen (*DIN*) in water bodies; NO_3^- . Within organisms, this nutrient must be reduced to ammonium (NH_4^+) prior to its use in the synthesis of amino acids for growth.

Osmotrophy – growth using dissolved organic matter (*DOM*), such as sugars and amino acids. Used by bacteria, but also by microalgae, especially in darkness.

Particulate organic matter (POM) – any solid organic form that is not living, such as faecal material, debris and corpses.

Photon – a package of light energy. Photons collide with a surface of a given area at a given rate, described as a photon flux density (PFD). Full sunlight has a PFD of visible light, as used to support photosynthesis, of ca. $2000 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.

Photosynthesis – the use of light energy to synthesize organic matter from CO_2 and H_2O . Gross photosynthesis is just that synthesis (primary production), while net photosynthesis subtracts any allied costs in respiration and especially costs in nitrate reduction required to support organism growth.

Phytoplankton – a type of *microalgae* (*cyanobacteria* or *protist*) that uses photosynthesis and osmotrophy. Many so-called phytoplankton are actually *mixoplankton*; mixoplankton can additionally eat.

Plankton – organisms that are unable to move against currents. This does not preclude them from being motile, and some can migrate vertically many 10s or even 100s m in the water column.

Primary production – production of new organic material in an ecosystem. Usually associated in aquatic ecosystem with *photosynthesis* due to the activity of *phytoplankton* and *mixoplankton*. Not all primary production enters biomass, however; a significant proportion may be leaked as dissolved organic matter (*DOM*) into the water and thence support the growth of (heterotrophy in) various microbes and especially bacteria.

Producer – an organism whose activity (*photosynthesis*) results in the net increase in the abundance of organic material in an ecosystem, by fixing CO₂.

Production – in ecology, making biomass. (See *primary production*.)

Protist – a general term for an extremely diverse range of eukaryote microbes. Most protists live suspended in the water as *plankton*, but many others live attached to particles rather than in suspension, and some are important parasites in other organisms (including humans). The diversity of protists exceeds that of all other eukaryotic organisms combined.

Pycnocline – an energy gradient based on water density (which usually results from a combination of temperature and/or salinity gradients). Above this, the water is well mixed (see, *mixed layer depth*)

Q₁₀ – temperature sensitivity coefficient (index) indicating the magnitude of the change in reaction rate over a range of temperature of 10°C. Typically, Q₁₀ is assumed to be 2; this means that if temperature is increased by 10°C then the reaction rate increases 2-fold (i.e., it doubles). In reality, Q₁₀ is a constant value over a narrow temperature range, with organism death occurring rapidly above a critical value.

Self shading – the loss of light supporting *photosynthesis* resulting from other light absorbing materials (typically, photo-pigment containing organisms) being closer to the light source and thus absorbing, removing, photons.

Simulation – a model output that has time as a variable.

Simulation model – a mathematical, computational, model which describes changes in the system over time as a fundamental feature.

Specific heat capacity - amount of heat energy required to raise the temperature by 1 unit. The unit is J Kg⁻¹ K⁻¹ (i.e., joules per Kg of material per Kelvin, noting that 1 Kelvin ≡ 1°C).

Spring bloom – the early seasonal (spring) growth of phototrophic organisms (*phytoplankton* and/or *mixoplankton*). The term 'bloom' is a subjective one but may be considered to reflect an increase in biomass abundance of ca. 10-fold over the background level.

Stoichiometry – relative quantities of components within substances. Often referenced to elemental quantities, such as relative amounts of carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus (i.e., C:N:P) in predator and prey.

Thermocline – a *pycnocline* based on a temperature gradient.

Trophic interactions – interactions between organisms in which energy and/or materials are transferred.

Water column – a vertical transect in a body of water, from the surface to an interface (typically either a *thermocline*, *pycnocline*, or the bottom).

Zooplankton – a type of plankton that feeds on other (prey) organisms, typically by ingesting either the whole prey, or significant components of it. Zooplankton may be characterised in different ways; protist vs metazoan zooplankton, meroplankton vs holoplankton. Protist zooplankton are typically fast-growing efficient unicellular microbes. Metazoan zooplankton are multicellular animals that range from microscopic to many m in length, and typically have complex life cycles. Meroplankton are larval stages of non-planktonic animals (such as barnacles, crabs, starfish); holoplankton are animals that are planktonic throughout their life.

Introduction

This work explores the effects of temperature upon aquatic ecosystems. It specifically develops this topic through reference to the planktonic life that inhabit freshwaters and marine systems.

Plankton comprise the life forms that produce the food needed by larger aquatic animals, through to fish, birds etc. The food web leading to these larger organisms depends critically upon the growth and success of different types (species) of plankton. Plankton are mainly microbial, typically each organism is less than 0.01mm long. Plankton cannot typically readily move to waters of different temperature. In essence, unless the organisms can effectively shut down so they can avoid extreme conditions (and many can enter resting stages to accomplish this), they have to survive and thrive in waters of changing temperature.

Temperature changes are the most obvious features of climate change, but of course temperature naturally changes also with the seasons and daily. Temperature changes experienced by aquatic organisms are much slower than those experienced by terrestrial organisms. This is because it takes a lot of energy to change the temperature of water. This reflects the high specific heat capacity of water; these are topics in chemistry and physics. The result is that water temperatures take a long time to increase and then to decrease – this is why in temperate areas, the warmest seawater temperatures are often in early autumn, and coldest in late winter or early spring.

The impacts of changes in temperature upon the growth of plankton is a highly complex topic, with a range of interconnected subjects. It is difficult to separate these subjects. Here models are used to help you better appreciate the effects.

CLASS ACTIVITY #1

On a white board, or similar, draw out a food web from nutrients through different photosynthetic aquatic organisms (algae), herbivores and carnivores. Link this around so that, through release of waste and decay, nutrients are recycled.

Assuming that temperature increases biological rate processes, for each of the links, consider how increases or decreases in temperature might affect the processes not only for that specific process but would have a ripple effect around the loop.

What pieces of information would you need to understand the problem better?

Temperature and Life

All life on Earth requires liquid water. This immediately constrains life to within 0-100°C (depending on salinity and elevation above sea level). But the ways that temperature affects life are far more complex than simply needing liquid water.

Growth; resources and energy

Organisms need to maintain themselves (repairing any damage), grow (increase in size) and reproduce. In addition, they may have other requirements such as moving around to locate light, nutrients or food, avoid predators, or indeed to live in the most favourable temperature. To achieve this, they need energy and resources which, through 100's of biochemical reactions, are exploited to generate living biomass.

Biochemistry

Biochemistry describes the chemistry of life. Every component of every organism is made from small molecules and assembled into larger components. For a primary producer, for example a photosynthetic organism like a microalga or a plant, the assembly process starts with inorganic compounds such as water (H₂O), carbon dioxide (CO₂) and various nutrients such as ammonium, nitrate and phosphate (NH₄⁺, NO₃⁻, PO₄³⁻, respectively). Oxygen (O₂) is a release product of photosynthesis. For a consumer, the process starts by disassembling the biomass ingested, which consumes energy and results in the release of waste materials. Importantly, most consumers also require O₂ to support energy production. Photosynthetic organisms also consume O₂ at night-time; in darkness they continue to operate biochemical systems and need energy to do so.

The control of physiology requires coordination and regulation. Many of the processes are controlled via complex feed-back and feed-forward interactions. The processes themselves are often enabled by enzymes.

Enzymes

Enzymes are biological compounds (typically proteins) that have a role in speeding up chemical reactions. The reactions mediated by a given enzyme are usually very specific, involving a few substances (substrates) that are brought together to react and produce a new compound. A common description of how an enzyme works is that the shape of the enzyme protein allows the substrates to fit into enzyme akin to keys fitting into a lock. The rate at which the reaction occurs depends on the concentration of the substrates and the affinity of the enzyme for the substrates. For maximum efficiency, the enzyme has a high maximum reaction rate and a high affinity. The higher the affinity (which means that the substrate fits the enzyme shape well) the less substrate is needed to enable the reaction to work quickly.

Fig.1 shows the relationship between substrate concentration and reaction rate for a generalised enzyme reaction.

Fig.1 Relationship between substrate concentration [S] and reaction rate (V). The rate of enzyme activity (V) against the substrate concentration, [S], is often described using what is called a *rectangular hyperbola*, or Michaelis-Menten curve. The equation is: $V = V_{max} \times \frac{[S]}{[S] + K_M}$. Here, V_{max} is the maximum possible rate, and K_M is the half-saturation constant. Note that in the equation the units of concentration for [S] cancel out, and the unit for K_M is the same as for [S], so the unit for V is the same as for V_{max} . The values of V_{max} and K_M in the plots are respectively for V_1 , 1 and 2, and for V_2 , 0.5 and 0.25. If you read the value of V achieved for a value of [S] that is equal to the value of K_M , you will note that the value of V is half the value of V_{max} ; this is why the value of K_M is termed the *half-saturation constant*.

There is another important factor controlling enzyme rates, and that is temperature.

Enzymes and temperature

Temperature affects how an enzyme works through two ways. Firstly, chemical reactions typically occur more rapidly at higher temperatures. Secondly, at high temperatures proteins denature; that means that their shape is changed. You can see how temperature affects proteins by watching the white of an egg cook; as the protein denatures it contracts and, in this instance, becomes white and hardened. If the shape of the enzyme changes, then the fit of the substrate 'key' into the protein 'lock' fails, and the enzyme no longer works.

What we expect to see when we measure a chemical reaction that involves an enzyme, is that the reaction rate initially increases as temperature increases, and then it passes a maximum (optimum) temperature point and the rate then decreases very rapidly.

In simple terms, the relationship between the reaction rate and temperature is often described through reference to what is termed a Q_{10} value. **Fig.2** shows the relationship between temperature and enzyme reaction rate for different values of Q_{10} . You can observe that if $Q_{10}=2$, then an increase in temperature by 10°C raises the reaction rate by a factor of 2 (i.e., x2, a doubling).

There is no indication here of a deterioration in the reaction rate at high temperature; in reality, denaturing of the enzyme would result in a rapid decline in reaction rate. At very low temperatures the reaction rate may decline more rapidly and of course no reaction will occur at freezing point as the water in which the biochemicals are dissolved will be solid.

A common exploitation of enzymes with different reaction optima may be seen in biological detergents, as used for washing clothes. These contain a mixture of enzymes that 'eat' different types of food spillages. The mixture is also selected to give a wide coverage of temperatures so that a single detergent can operate at temperatures ranging from ca. $10 - 90^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Fig.2 Effect of temperature on reaction rate V . The equation defining the curves is $V = V_{rt} \times Q_{10}^{(T-T_{rt})/10}$, where V_{rt} is the reaction rate at reference temperature, T_{rt} , T is the current temperature, and Q_{10} is the increase in reaction rate per 10°C . Here, $T_{rt} = 20^{\circ}\text{C}$, $V_{rt} = 1$, and Q_{10} takes the values indicated; this is why all the curves pass through the point 20,1.

Biochemical processes involved in building and operating an organism involve 100s of reactions with a similar number of enzymes. Every enzyme has its own reaction rates, substrate affinities and temperature-rate relationships. Q_{10} values for each reaction vary around the assumed typical value of 2, and the optimal temperature beyond which the enzyme fails also differs. Even under optimal conditions, enzymes do not last for ever – they need to be replaced. The more frequently they are

used, the more quickly they will fail. So, while temperature increases the enzyme reaction rate, it also increases the rate at which enzymes fail and have to be replaced. The old, failed enzyme is itself pulled apart and recycled, though that costs energy.

How the whole organism grows at different temperatures thus depends on how temperature affects the sum of all of the individual reactions in its biochemistry. It is also affected by other factors such as how temperature alters the structure of the membranes surrounding the cell and (for eukaryotes) the organelles. Depending on the chemical composition of the lipid bilayer in those membranes, temperature affects fluidity of that membrane and therefore how readily chemicals can pass through it. You can likely readily appreciate how all of this complexity impacts the response of a whole organism to temperature changes.

Organism growth and temperature

The relationship between growth and temperature for any given organism is broadly similar to that we see for an individual enzyme reaction and temperature. That is, as temperature increases, so (assuming all else is optimal) growth increases up until a maximum rate is attained at the optimal temperature. As temperature continues to increase, the growth rate declines very rapidly followed by death. It may require only the failure of one critical enzymic reaction for death to occur.

Within a certain narrow range (ca., 5-10°C), the relationship between temperature and organism growth rate may be described using a Q_{10} value (similar to **Fig.2**). However, the full description is more complex and may involve a ramping up stage at low temperatures (below a critical temperature the organism may enter stasis, essentially going to sleep), the 'Q₁₀' phase is most likely not a set value, and then there is the sudden decline at temperatures above the optimal. The reason that the 'Q₁₀' phase is not as one may expect is because as temperature increases so the maintenance costs increase as well.

Fig.3 gives example plots of temperature-growth rate relationships. Here, you can see a ramping up from a zero-growth rate at very low temperature to the low extreme for active growth (zone (i)). There is then a phase of a more gradual increase in growth rate with temperature, rather similar to the Q_{10} relationship shown in **Fig.2** (zone (ii)) up to the maximum at the optimum temperature. Beyond that there is a rapid decline to death (zone (iii)).

The equations describing the shapes of the curves shown in **Fig.3** are complex and will not be expanded here.

The values of Q_{10} shown in **Fig.3** have been calculated from the following equation:

$$Q_{10} = \left(\frac{U}{U_{optT}} \right)^{\left(\frac{10}{(T-T_{opt})} \right)}$$

U_{optT} is the maximum growth rate as measured at the optimal temperature, T_{opt} . U is the maximum growth rate at temperature T .

Written in the syntax of a spreadsheet (e.g., Excel), this reads as:

$$Q10=(U/UoptT)^(10/(T-Topt))$$

Fig.3 Example effects of temperature on organism growth rates. These plots are shown for two examples, species 1 (Sp1) and species 2 (Sp2). The top graph (a) shows the description of a normalised relationship, in which the maximum value (of T_{reg}) is 1; this allows a ready comparison of the relative effects of temperature on the different organisms. The middle graph (b) relates that normalised curve form to the actual growth rate (U_{max}). The bottom graph (c) shows the calculated values of Q_{10} . Zone (i) shows an initial ramping up of response, zone (ii) is the normal growth range, where $Q_{10} \approx 2$, and zone (iii) is where denaturing of proteins and thence death occurs. Note that although there is a period of relative stability in those Q_{10} values (between the lower and optimum temperature values) the values are neither actually constant nor simply relatable to Q_{10} as presented in Fig.2. As shown here, both species have an optimal temperature (T_{opt} of 20°C). Sp1 has a lower minimum temperature for active growth (12 rather than 14°C), is less sensitive to temperature (note the lower slope of the curves between the minimum and optimum temperatures) and a lower maximum growth rate at the optimal temperature (U_{optT} of 0.9 rather than 1, as shown in the graph of the maximum growth rate, U_{max}).

Efficiency, organism size and evolution to life at higher temperatures

Organisms evolve to balance out efficiencies across all of their processes. What this means is that we expect an organism to evolve to match its maximum growth rate (U_{optT} in the previous section) with the potential of the surrounding environment to deliver that growth rate. The reason is that an inability to match the supply of resources (such as nutrients) with the demand for those resources to support growth causes stress to an organism, making it more likely to die. In essence, the organism evolves to grow within its means.

An example of this is that an organism evolved to grow in a low-nutrient environment has no need to be able to grow very rapidly as it cannot do so. Conversely, an organism in a high-nutrient environment will evolve to grow rapidly to make best use of the resources. This evolution can be seen in cultures of microalgae grown in special types of vessel called a chemostat; a chemostat forces an organism to grow at a rate set by the scientist. If we grow the same organism in 'fast' versus 'slow' chemostats, after many months the organisms from the 'slow' chemostat will have evolved and they can no longer grow as quickly as those grown in the 'fast' chemostat.

Now, if we consider similar ecosystems operating at a higher temperature then we may initially expect growth to be quicker and thence nutrients to be exhausted more rapidly. However, that would result in organisms becoming more stressed. In consequence, we expect organisms growing in environments with a higher typical temperature to evolve so that their maximum growth rate at the higher typical temperature (i.e., value of U_{optT}) becomes lower.

What this means is that, while every organism may be expected to have a temperature-growth curve of the form similar to that shown in **Fig.3**, the maximum growth rate achievable under optimal temperature conditions will vary depending on other features of the environment, such as typical nutrient or food availability.

To make matters more complicated, if all else is assumed to be equal, because enzymes work faster at higher temperatures, less enzyme is needed to support a given growth rate. Because enzymes are such a fundamental component of a cell's makeup, the total impact of this is that organisms growing at higher temperatures can be smaller than comparable organisms growing at lower temperatures. Such changes in organism size have other implications because a smaller cell needs less resources and it may also represent a less favourable food item (for a consumer, it is generally preferable to spend energy on capturing fewer larger prey items than to waste it on capturing many smaller prey).

Food webs and temperature

From the above it will be apparent that temperature, through its effects on each organism type in an ecosystem, has the potential to have a profound impact on the operation of a food web. Through an indirect impact, that will be so in planktonic ecosystems even if all the organisms have a similar temperature-growth relationship because of the effect that temperature has on water column stability and hence on the availability of nutrients. In reality, though, the temperature-growth relationships for each organism will not be the same with respect to the optimal temperature, the low temperature value, and the slope (akin to Q_{10}) between those optimal and low extremes. Whether an organism enters some form of dormancy at low temperature or continues to grow at an ever slower pace at lower temperatures will also have an important effect. Conditions promoting emergence from dormancy, if applicable, will likewise be important.

There is, however, another important link between temperature and organism growth that will also impact food web functioning, and that relates to the water solubility of the oxygen required by the organisms for their growth.

CLASS ACTIVITY #2

Revisit Class Activity #1, but this time consider the links between the processes in the context of the temperature-rate graphs shown in **Fig.3**.

What might happen if different linkages had different temperature profiles? That is, the lower, optimum and upper bounds of each profile (akin to **Fig.3a**) differs.

Oxygen solubility in water and temperature

Oxygen is essential for all organisms with an aerobic metabolism - that includes most planktonic organisms and the animals that feed on them. These organisms obtain oxygen dissolved in the water in which they live. Oxygen enters the water as a waste product of photosynthesis and is consumed through its use to support aerobic respiration. There is also an exchange of oxygen by diffusion from the atmosphere and adjoining water bodies. Also, if the concentration of oxygen is so high that it can no longer dissolve at the local water pressure (so the event is most likely at the very surface where pressure is lowest), it may bubble out which is termed out-gassing. The loss of oxygen by out-gassing occurs as a consequence of 'supersaturation'; it occurs literally as bubbles only at the very surface of the water, as below the surface the water pressure raises the solubility of oxygen in the water.

The exchange in oxygen (O_2) between the atmosphere and the water through diffusion depends on the gradient of O_2 concentrations (i.e., the concentration in the air versus that in the water) and is greatly affected by disturbance of the water surface by waves and wind. Windy conditions and higher temperatures increase the transfer rate (**Fig.4**).

Fig.4 Relationship between the oxygen transfer coefficient and wind speed (m s^{-1}) at different temperatures.

However, the direction of that transfer (in or out of the water) depends on the concentration of O_2 in the water (that in the atmosphere being considered essentially constant). Specifically, it relates to the solubility of O_2 .

The solubility of O_2 depends on both temperature and salinity, as well as pressure (i.e., water depth). As temperature increases, so the solubility declines (**Fig.5**). The saline seawater saturates at a lower concentration of O_2 .

Fig.5 Relationship between oxygen saturation and temperature for freshwater and seawater (0 and 35 salinity, respectively) at zero depth (water surface). Indicated on the graph is the level at which aerobic organisms typically show symptoms of stress through a lack of oxygen; below this level the water is considered to be hypoxic.

Below a certain concentration, typically considered as $<2\text{mg O}_2\text{ L}^{-1}$ ($<2\text{g O}_2\text{ m}^{-3}$), a state of hypoxia is achieved, and organisms (especially highly active animals such as fish) are increasingly likely to be stressed and to die.

In the absence of any other factor affecting oxygen consumption, one may think that such a condition could not be reached; the O_2 released during the photosynthesis that fixes CO_2 into the organic compounds that make organisms would simply be consumed when those organics are mineralised (converted back to CO_2). However, as we have seen, an excess O_2 leaves the water column. In addition, the biomass can all accumulate deeper in the water away from the atmosphere. This creates an imbalance in supply and demand for oxygen.

The amount of O_2 required to support the conversion of organics back to CO_2 is the **biological oxygen demand** (BOD). BOD is expressed in units of O_2 concentration. BOD technically, as determined in water quality tests, only considers the microbial (mainly bacterial) consumption of oxygen during the growth of those microbes on organic matter in the water. That organic matter exists in dissolved and particulate forms (dissolve organic matter, DOM; particulate organic matter, POM). In the real world, however, there are other sources and sinks of O_2 such that BOD may under- or overestimate the risk of hypoxia. Notably, as considered below, these factors are affected by temperature.

Photosynthesis produces O_2 . The problem arises when a proportion of that O_2 produced during photosynthesis (termed 'primary production') leaves the system before the consumer activity

occurs. When this happens, the BOD exceeds the O₂ availability. There are two obvious mechanisms that could create such a condition:

- 1) the primary production is so great in the surface waters that more O₂ is produced than can be contained within the water. There is then a loss of O₂ through outgassing, either as diffusion, or in more extreme conditions of oxygen super-saturation, as bubbles of O₂.
- 2) the temperature increases so that the solubility of O₂ declines. This again promotes outgassing of O₂ to the atmosphere.

As the rate of photosynthesis increases with a temperature increase, both conditions may be met simultaneously. In both instances the BOD in total (i.e., not just microbial consumption of DOM and POM, but also respiration by other organisms) can then exceed the availability of O₂.

It is not as simple as that though, because the balance between O₂ production and entry vs O₂ consumption and escape depends on the rates of various processes. For example, if the wind velocity is high enough then the entry of O₂ from the atmosphere may be increased sufficiently (see **Fig.4**) to prevent or delay the onset of hypoxia. Or the type of material being degraded by the consumers may be more complex so that the rate of consumption of O₂ is less than it would be if the material was more rapidly degraded; again, this may enable diffusion of O₂ into the system to balance demands from the consumers.

The situation can be made more problematic if eutrophication promotes higher biomass levels and (simultaneously) there is an additional disruption to the usual food web interactions due to the temperature-related death of organisms. For an introduction to the topic of eutrophication, please see:

Flynn, K. J. (2024). Exploring eutrophication – polluting with too much of a good thing; a teaching guide. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12529789>

CLASS ACTIVITY #3

*Revisit Class Activity #2 but now consider which processes generate and consume oxygen. Remember that activities producing oxygen can only raise the oxygen concentration to a set amount as a function of temperature (**Fig.5**). And also remember that processes that consume oxygen are limited by the amount of biomass to consume or decay.*

Sketch out versions of the food web, annotated with changing temperature and nutrient load, that may lead to conditions of oxygen saturation or to hypoxia.

Putting it all together – building a conceptual model

Studying how the processes introduced above all interact is complex. It is especially so because the system is dynamic. In nature, much additional complexity and variability is introduced by the weather. The weather affects the system through changing conditions for the growth of the organisms (such as affecting temperature and gas exchange rates for O₂ between the water and the air, and the amount of light that supports photosynthesis) and through other events such as flash-flooding resulting in a sudden influx of nutrients into the water which causes (or further enhances) eutrophication.

To explore these interactions, we can use a simulation model. A model is a simplification of reality, while a simulation is a simplified representation of reality that involves changes over time.

The biological components of the model used here are shown in **Fig.6**. Growth of the microalgae, which is the primary producer, is limited by nutrient availability. That nutrient is considered as inorganic nitrogen (such as ammonium). The zooplankton consume the microalgae, their growth being limited by the abundance of the microalgae, releasing ammonium directly back to the nutrient pool for reuse by the microalgae, while another portion is released as faeces. Faeces represent a form of particulate organic matter (POM). Other contributions to the POM are dead microalgae and zooplankton; death of these organisms occurs in the model if the temperature becomes too high (see **Fig.3**). The POM is consumed by bacteria (not shown), with their growth resulting in the release of ammonium. The whole model thus describes the flow of nitrogen (N) around the system.

Fig.6 Simple representation of a food chain as used in the model. Here, nutrient nitrogen is used by microalgae (photosynthetic organisms), and these organisms are eaten by zooplankton. Zooplankton do not convert all the ingested microalgae into their own biomass; there is a direct release of nutrients (similar to the release of urine by animals such as humans) and also via the decay of wastes released as faeces. Faeces are a form of particulate organic matter (POM). Microalgae and zooplankton that die (black arrows) also contribute to POM. Bacteria (not shown) degrade the POM and the nitrogen in the POM that they release during the consumption of POM then re-enters the nutrient pool. Microalgal growth (phototrophy) generates oxygen, while zooplankton and the decay of POM (heterotrophy) consume oxygen. Increased temperature (within bounds) increases the rates of growth and other interactions (Zone (ii) in **Fig.3**). Increased temperature also decreases the solubility of oxygen in water (**Fig.4**). Excess oxygen above the solubility limit leaves the water, so that during decay the heterotrophic activity can decrease oxygen in the water to dangerously low levels (hypoxia).

Factors that can be changed in the model include:

- maximum growth rates of the microalgae and zooplankton
- optimum temperature for growth
- low temperature for growth
- sensitivity of growth to temperature

The effects that these can have are shown in **Fig.3**. The sensitivity can be seen in the slope of the curves in the T_{reg} panel in **Fig.3**, with species 2 being more sensitive (having a steeper slope in the curve form between the low and optimum temperatures). A higher sensitivity gives a higher Q_{10} value (see the Q_{10} panel in **Fig.3**).

The temperature-growth relationship is also used to control the death rate of the organisms should the temperature exceed the optimum. Specifically, the value of T_{reg} (see **Fig.3a**) is used in an equation that defines the death rate (D_u) as:

$$D_u = IF(T > T_{opt}, (1 - T_{reg}) * U_{optT})$$

This calculates a death rate (D_u) only when T is greater than the optimum (T_{opt}) as $1 - T_{reg}$ multiplied by the maximum growth rate U_{optT} . This means that the faster an organism can grow, the faster it also dies. Note from the example plots of T_{reg} in **Fig.3**, that T_{reg} decreases to zero rapidly as $T > T_{opt}$. Dead organism biomass contributes to the POM, and hence to the decay processes that release nutrient and also consume oxygen (**Fig.6**).

As external configurable factors, the model includes:

- setting the initial concentration of the nutrient pool
- introducing an additional amount of nutrient (akin to a pollution or flash-flood event) at a specific time
- configuring changes to the water temperature during the simulation
- setting the wind speed (this affects the rate of O_2 exchange between the water and the atmosphere).

For more information about the model and how its construction relates to reality, see the section **Caveats**.

Consult the QUICK START documentation to download the software and simulation model.

Operating the model

The model interface comprises four pages; these are described in detail below.

You can switch between these at any time by clicking the appropriate button on the left-hand side of the screen.

You may likely wish to alter the magnification (zoom) on each page to best display it on your screen. There is a 'fit' option available as the final option in the drop-down menu (top left of screen) for the zoom %.

The plots auto-scale at the end of the simulation. To rescale during the run, press 'F9' on your keyboard.

Using the print screen (**prt sc** or **PrtScn**) option on your PC provides a means to copy your results to another application (Word, PowerPoint, Excel etc). Remember to copy the *Configure* page as well as the results for each simulation so you have a record for what you have done!

Learning Outcomes (introduction) page

The screenshot shows a web browser window titled 'Powersim Simulation Presentation' at 100% zoom. The main content area is titled 'Getting too warm: exploring effects of temperature upon aquatic ecosystems'. On the left, there is a navigation menu with buttons for 'Learning Outcomes', 'Configure', 'Results', and 'Details'. The 'Learning Outcomes' section contains the following text:

This model allows you to explore some of the implications of temperature upon plankton growth. It considers a simple nutrient-microalgae-zooplankton food-chain (Fig.1), to which different amounts of nutrient can be added, and the implications explored under different temperature regimes, including deoxygenation of the water.

Learning outcomes:

- 1) understand that each organism has its own growth relationship with temperature and hence that interactions between organisms change with temperature.
- 2) understand that interactions between nutrient loading, temperature and ecology can result in changes in the oxygen content of the water that can lead to death of organisms in that ecosystem.

Below the text are logos for PML Plymouth Marine Laboratory, the European Union, UKRI Innovate UK, and ARKdynamics. A small disclaimer box states: 'Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. UK participants in Horizon Europe Project ProBleu [101113001] are supported by UKRI grant number 10081234 Plymouth Marine Laboratory.'

On the right, a diagram (Fig.1) illustrates a food chain with four components: Nutrient (blue box), Microalgae (green box), Zooplankton (red box), and POM (particulate organic matter, orange dashed box). Arrows show the flow: Nutrient to Microalgae, Microalgae to Zooplankton, Zooplankton to POM, and POM to Nutrient. Black arrows indicate that both Microalgae and Zooplankton contribute to POM.

Fig.1 A very simple representation of a food chain. Here, nutrient nitrogen is used by microalgae (photosynthetic organisms), and these organisms are eaten by zooplankton. Zooplankton do not convert all of the ingested microalgae into their own biomass; there is a direct release of nutrients (similar to the release of urine by animals such as humans) and also via the decay of wastes released as faeces. Faeces are a form of particulate organic matter (POM). Microalgae and zooplankton that die (black arrows) also contribute to POM. Bacteria (not shown) degrade the POM and the nitrogen in the POM re-enters the nutrient pool.

Microalgal growth (phototrophy) generates oxygen, while zooplankton and the decay of POM (heterotrophy) consumes oxygen.

Increased temperature (within bounds) increases the rates of growth and other interactions. Increased temperature also decreases the solubility of oxygen. Excess oxygen above the solubility limit, leaves the water (entering the atmosphere), so that during decay the heterotrophic activity can decrease oxygen in the water to dangerously low levels (hypoxia).

This gives an overview of the model and of the learning outcomes.

Proceed to the *Configure* page, by clicking the 'Configure' button.

Configure page

This is where you configure the abiotic components (nutrients, wind, temperature) and biotic components (related to microalgae and zooplankton).

Pressing **Ctrl+R** will reset the model, clearing the plots. Make sure you have copied any information that you need before doing so!

Configuring the model is achieved by moving the sliders. If you click above or below the current slider position, the slider will jump by a set amount; this can provide a quicker and more reproducible means to achieve a required setting.

The action of each slider is described below:

- **Nutrient** – this sets the initial amount of nutrient in the system. The units are as mgN m^{-3} , which is the same numeric value as $\mu\text{gN L}^{-1}$. If you want to convert to units as μM , divide this number by 14 (the molecular weight of N). The scale on the slider helps to convert to μM ; $140 \text{ mgN m}^{-3} = 10 \mu\text{M}$.
- **Wind** – this sets the wind speed. The units are as m s^{-1} . The higher the wind speed the more rapidly the O_2 level in the water equilibrates with that in the air (see [Fig.4](#)).
- **Pulse** – this sets the additional nutrient concentration added to the system to simulate a pollution event. The units are as mgN m^{-3} , which is the same numeric value as $\mu\text{gN L}^{-1}$. If you want to convert to units as μM , divide this number by 14 (the molecular weight of N). The scale on the slider helps to convert to μM ; $280 \text{ mgN m}^{-3} = 20 \mu\text{M}$.
- **Pulse time** – this sets the time of the pulse nutrient addition. The unit is day.
- **Temperature sliders (T@0d .. T@150d)** – these set the temperature at a given day. For example, to set the temperature on day 100 at 20°C , drag the slider for T@100d to 20. For simplicity, temperatures between the set points are assumed to change in a linear fashion. The graph underneath these sliders will, once the model has been run, show the temperature over the whole 150d period.

Sliders controlling the configurations of the microalgae (green) and zooplankton (red) are arranged one above the other.

- **Optimum** – these set the optimum temperature for growth as $^\circ\text{C}$. For reference, see [Fig.3](#).

- **Range** – these set the temperature range between the lowest temperature for effective growth and the optimum as °C. See **Fig.3**.
- **Sensitivity** – these set the sensitivity of the temperature-growth relationship. A higher value makes the organism more sensitive to temperature. See the T_{reg} panel in **Fig.3a**; the higher the sensitivity the steeper is the slope of the temperature-growth relationship. This gives a higher Q_{10} value (see the Q_{10} panel in **Fig.3c**).
- **Umax** – these set the maximum growth rate of the organism. A higher value makes the organism grow faster. The unit is d^{-1} ; a value of $0.693 d^{-1}$ allows the organism biomass to double each day. The maximum growth rate can only be attained when the temperature is at the optimum, and also if the availability of nutrient (for the microalgae) or food (for the zooplankton) is sufficient to meet the needs of the organism.

To the right of the sliders for the organisms are two graphs for each organism type. These graphs show:

- **Treg vs °C** – the value of T_{reg} (see **Fig.3a**) is a normalized growth rate; a value of 1 indicates optimal temperature conditions.
- **UmT vs °C** – this plot shows the same as the T_{reg} vs °C graph, but now it shows the actual maximum growth rate (rather than the normalized rate) at a given temperature. See **Fig.3b**.

The graphs will show the relationships as they emerge during the simulation at the end of the run.

Normally you would switch to the Results or Details page before playing the simulation.

To play, either use the run button on the control panel (top left of screen) or press **Ctrl+Space**.

Results page

This page contains 3 graphs, all of which have time as the x-axis. If you watch these graphs during the simulation, you will observe the changes. If you want to pause the simulation at any point, press **Ctrl+Space**. Press again to continue the simulation. The run-time is shown in the bottom righthand corner of the display.

The graphs show the following:

- **Temperature vs time** – this is the same plot as shown under the temperature sliders on the *Configure* page, and reproduces the conditions that you have selected.
- **Amount vs time** – this shows plots of nutrient, microalgal biomass, zooplankton biomass, and of POM, all with units of mgN m^{-3} . This are the components of the model as shown in the boxes in **Fig.6**. From this you can watch the predator-prey interactions. You can also see the addition of the nutrient pulse; in the screen shot shown here, that pulse occurred at 55d, adding the 252 mgN m^{-3} as set by the Pulse slider.
- **Oxygen** – this shows the concentration of O_2 in the water. The units are $\text{g O}_2 \text{ m}^{-3}$; the numeric value is thus the same as for $\text{mg O}_2 \text{ L}^{-1}$. The green line shows the saturation value for seawater at the temperature shown in the Temperature vs time graph. The other part shows the simulated actual O_2 concentration. The colour bar on the right-hand end indicates where hypoxia develops (i.e., red indicates danger in the $<2 \text{ g O}_2 \text{ m}^{-3}$ range). If the O_2 level dips down into that zone, then in reality there would be an increasing risk of death of the plankton and especially of larger animals.

Details page

This page contains 2 blocks of graphs; the left-hand block all show time as the x-axis, while the right-hand block all have temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) as the x-axis. If you watch these graphs during the simulation, you will observe the changes as they occur over the simulation time.

If you want to pause the simulation at any point, press **Ctrl+Space**. Press again to continue the simulation. The run-time is shown in the bottom right-hand corner of the display.

The left-hand graphs show the following:

- **Temperature vs time** – this is the same plot as shown under the temperature sliders on the *Configure* page, and also the uppermost of the *Results* graphs.
- **Treg vs time** – this graph plots the normalized growth rate for each organism; a value of 1 indicates optimal temperature conditions (see [Fig.3a](#)).
- **Growth rate vs time** – this graph plots the potential maximum growth rate at the current temperature (UmT), and the actual growth rate (u) for the microalgae (Alg) and zooplankton (Zoo). The difference between u and UmT indicates nutrient or food limitations for the organisms. The unit is d^{-1} ; a value of 0.693 d^{-1} indicates a doubling of biomass each day. A negative value indicates a loss of biomass due to respiration exceeding the input of energy; while this could include, or lead to, organism death, there is a specific loss due to high temperature indicated separately in the graph below the growth graph.
- **Death rate vs time** – this graph plots the temperature-related death rates as they change during the simulation time. These will only show anything if the temperature exceeds the optimal temperature setting for that organism. The unit is d^{-1} ; a value of 0.693 d^{-1} indicates a halving of biomass each day due to death. The derivation of the death rate is explained in the description of the model (*'Putting it all together'*).

The right-hand graphs are arranged with the microalgae graphs uppermost, and the zooplankton graphs below. Note that, because the x-axis is temperature, if the temperature is constant, these graphs will likely show just a single data point!

- **Treg vs °C** – the value of Treg (see [Fig.3a](#)) is a normalized growth rate; a value of 1 indicates optimal temperature conditions. This is the same plot as in the *Configure* page.
- **UmT vs °C** – these graphs show the same as those in the corresponding Treg vs °C graph, but now it shows the actual maximum growth rate (rather than the normalized rate) at a given temperature. This is the same plot as in the *Configure* page. (see also [Fig.3b](#))
- **Du vs °C** – these graphs show the temperature-related death rates. These will only show anything if the temperature exceeds the optimal temperature setting for that organism (i.e., if the temperature is in Zone (iii) as shown in [Fig.3](#)).

Conducting experiments

The model provides you with many options to explore. Although this looks complex, it remains very much simpler than a real system (see the section **Caveats**).

Setting hypotheses

It is generally considered as good practice to, wherever possible, only change one thing at a time, or at least to keep as many things as possible constant. While that is impossible in the real world, it is quite possible when using a model. This allows you to test hypotheses relatively easily. However, whether your tests would apply to the real world depends on whether you trust the model. See the section **Caveats** to help you consider this matter further.

A **hypothesis** is rather like an educated guess. A hypothesis is worded along the lines of:

*H₁ If this factor is changed then I expect **this** and **that** to happen.*

This is looking for an association between variables.

You could split this into two hypotheses:

*H₁ If this factor is changed then I expect **this** to happen.*

*H₂ If this factor is changed then I expect **that** to happen.*

You should set a null hypothesis as well as a hypothesis. This is worded along the lines of:

*H₀ If this factor is changed then I expect **this** and **that** to not happen.*

The null hypothesis is looking for the lack of an association between variables. Note that the null hypothesis is indicated as 'H₀'.

Even when using a model, the answers to your tests may not be straightforward. This is because, just as in the real world, linkages between factors may be non-linear, or they may be distant, separated in space or time. This means that a small change in a factor may have little (an insignificant) effect, while a larger change in a factor may have a very large, disproportionate effect (and vice versa), or the consequence may be seen at some time in the future from when the factor was changed.

You should also be aware that effects may be positive (increasing a factor increases a response), or negative (increasing a factor decreases a response), and hence that combinations of factors may cancel each other. Or they provide a multiplicative (synergistic) effect and make the situation much worse, or perhaps better, than you expected.

The following makes some suggestions for the types of experiments you can conduct. You can, of course, make your own experiments.

You cannot break the model. The worst that can happen is that you would need to reload the model and start again. If you encounter a problem with the model, please contact the author so that we can endeavour to rectify the problem.

Note: to quickly set sliders to a position, click just above or below the slider, and it will jump to the next position. This is easier and more accurate than dragging the slider!

Note: remember to note your results before trying another test! A quick way of doing this is to copy the screen (use **prt sc**, on the keyboard) and paste the image into another application, such as Powerpoint, Word or Excel.

Starting off

The following would test hypotheses centred on what happens in systems running with high or low nutrients, high or low (but stable) temperatures, and high or low wind speed.

- Set the temperature parameters for the microalgae and zooplankton the same, with the optimal temperature at either 20 or 25°C.
- Set the temperature sliders all to 10°C
- Set wind to 0 m s⁻¹
- Set the pulse slider to 0 mgN m⁻³; there will then be no pollution pulse of nutrients.
- Set the nutrient slider to 28 mgN m⁻³
- Set the maximum growth rate (U_{max}) sliders at 1 d⁻¹ and 1.5 d⁻¹ for microalgae and zooplankton, respectively. This means that, under optimal conditions, the zooplankton can grow faster than the microalgae.
- Run the model and note what happens.
- Now, set the nutrient slider to 280 mgN m⁻³, and re-run the model.
- Now repeat again, with low and then high nutrients, and with the wind set to 10 m s⁻¹.
- Now repeat all the above but after you have increased the temperature sliders all to 20°C

You should have noted changes in the oscillations in the predator-prey populations, and also in the oxygen concentrations.

More complex experiments

Building from the above, explore what happens when the following configurations are used in conjunction with the suggestions made in *Starting off*. You can mix-and-match these suggestions as you wish. However, do not do this blindly; set a hypothesis and try and think out what might happen before running the simulations.

- Try different values for U_{max} for each of the organism groups; how do these affect the stability of the interactions?
- Make the temperature increase over the duration of the simulation, perhaps beyond the optimal temperature set for one or both of the organisms.
- What happens if you try a series of temperature changes, up-and-down, or down-and-up?
- Introduce a nutrient (pollution) pulse earlier or later in the simulation, of a large or a small addition. How does this affect a system that is originally a low nutrient configuration versus a high nutrient configuration? What happens if the wind is high or low during the pollution event? What happens if temperature is fluctuating so that it affects the growth (and perhaps death) rates of the organisms during the pollution event?
- Try and specifically locate combinations of conditions that would act to create a hypoxic event. One such set of conditions is visible using the settings shown in the screenshots of the different pages in the **Operating the model** section. Note that the oxygen level in the screenshot of the *Results* page dips down into the <2 g O₂ m⁻³ zone; such low levels could cause fish kills, for example.

Caveats

A caveat is a warning concerning limitations applying to a situation. In this context, we are considering how simplifications or assumptions made in the formulation of the model affect the reliability of your interpretations of the results and in hypothesis testing. This is important when you use any experimental system, whether it is in a test tube, an aquarium, wildlife park or a mathematical model; it is always very important to ask how the system compares to the reality that you are trying to understand.

Here, you have used a simple model of a very complex system. To decide how realistic are the results you need to consider two things:

- what features are not included
- whether the features that are included are described appropriately

As a word of warning, it is very difficult to balance simplicity and realism in simulation models. It is also very easy to look at a list of excluded features and conclude that the model is so simple that it simply does not, and cannot, provide anything useful. Against that, you need to appreciate that science develops as much by finding faults as it does by finding solutions; this is why the null hypothesis (H_0) is arguably more important than the hypotheses H_1 , H_2 .

Another way of considering this issue of trusting your results is that if you ventured into the field, and studied a real plankton ecosystem, it is extremely unlikely that you would be able to measure many parameters with any great accuracy or temporal resolution. Most likely you would take a few organism counts and nutrient samples from a few locations just once a day. Those organism counts need to be converted into biomass units in order to use them in any meaningful way to work out how nutrients flow through an ecosystem, and that step is typically not even attempted by scientists.

So, while it is easy to criticise (caveat) a modelling study, it is easier still to caveat a study of a real ecosystem! We are then limited to establishing general rules for explaining what we see in nature.

Excluded features

- **Light-dark and changing weather conditions** – the model makes no assumptions about the availability of light other than to assume it is non-limiting to growth of the microalgae. As microalgal populations grow, so they colour the water. That event, which is more important at higher nutrient levels, causes self-shading of those microalgae living deeper in the water column. Inevitably, then, light does become limiting, unless the nutrient levels are not too high and/or that the assumed water depth is shallow. Light may also become limiting due to cloud cover and, of course, at night. The importance of night is problematic if there is insufficient light during the day for the organisms to accumulate an adequate reserve of C. Many microalgae grow little faster under continuous illumination than under a light-dark cycle provided the light available is non-limiting. Microalgae also contribute to the consumption of oxygen during night.
- **Mixed layer depth** – this relates firstly to the availability of light (see above), but also to the topic of O_2 exchange with the atmosphere and release from photosynthesis (at the surface) balanced against O_2 consumption which may be most important at depth. This may mean that hypoxia may develop more readily at depth, and especially below the mixed layer.

- **Bacteria** – bacteria are not explicitly described in the model, though their activity (through the degradation of POM) is described with its attendant consumption of O₂ and release of nutrients. In general terms, the activity of a given bacterial species is affected by temperature in the same fashion that other organisms are affected. However, bacterial communities possess such variety that one may assume that if one species is ill suited to grow at a given temperature, other species will take their place. The limiting factor for bacteria then becomes substrate availability (i.e., in the model, how much POM is present).
- **Other nutrients and multi-nutrient interactions** – only a single nutrient is considered here, nitrogen. In reality, phosphorus, iron and silicate are also important potentially limiting nutrients. Furthermore, nutrients stresses can interact with each other and promote other events such as the development of toxicity or production of mucus which can create additional demands for O₂ during its decay.

Adequacy of the description of included features

- **Closed system** – for pragmatic reasons the system described here is closed except for atmosphere-water gas exchange: there is no flow through of water carrying nutrients or organisms. The whole structure is akin to that in a shallow saline pond where any evaporation is countered by addition of freshwater to make good the loss. The simulation period, 150d or half a year, assumes all other climatic events other than temperature remain constant; this is not plausible as a description of the real world.
- **Descriptions of the plankton, nutrient and food limitations** – as far as it goes, assuming a single primary producer and consumer with a single limiting nutrient, the description is sufficient. These styles of model have a long history of being able to describe plankton dynamics at least to a first approximation. However, an important simplification is that there is assumed to be a fixed ratio between carbon and nitrogen in the composition of microalgae and zooplankton. This fixed ratio of C:N (such ratios are termed '*stoichiometric ratios*') represents a gross simplification with far reaching consequences for oxygen cycling (see below) and also for interactions between the microalgae and zooplankton. The reason is that when a microalgae exhausts the nitrogen nutrient, it continues to photosynthesise, laying down starch or lipids; in doing so its C:N ratio increases. Microalgae with high C:N are not such good food for zooplankton; what is ingested is not digested so efficiently, and often such organisms are not eaten so readily. The microalgae may even become toxic. Such events can create a feedback loop which in extreme cases can lead to the formation of a microalgal bloom that just resides in the water column and is not eaten. Such a bloom is often termed a *Harmful Algal Bloom*. The bloom can continue to add organic carbon to the system, raising the BOD, so when the microalgae eventually die, the likelihood of hypoxia increases.
- **Recycling of POM** – this is assumed to be a simple function of POM abundance, with no explicit description of the microbial communities that would be involved in POM decay and conversion of the nitrogen within it back to nutrient-N for use by the microalgae. Again, this approach is commonly used in models, and importantly it gives the expected delay between the production of POM and the conversion to nutrient-N.
- **Oxygen dynamics** – the equations for gas exchange and solubility are standard research descriptions, but the descriptions for biological production and consumption assume fixed C:N stoichiometry. As discussed above, this simplification means that the results of the simulation underestimate the risks presented by hypoxia. Deeper water is also more likely to

become hypoxic or anoxic as dead material sinks to the bottom, further away from the water-atmosphere interface where O₂ exchanges.

Conclusions

The model is very simple. It is sufficient to provide an introduction to the topics (consistent with the learning objectives), but it is not suitable for site-specific projections.

To check how the model may be developed to better simulate reality, see the 'Modifications to the model' subsection in *'What you should have noted'*.

What you should have noted

This section gives an overview of the primary learning points and other features that should have been uncovered during your experiments.

Temperature effects – the basics

Temperature affects life in aquatic ecosystems through several routes:

- **Temperature affects the stability of the water column.** Warm water floats on top of cooler water, so when the water is warmed by energy from sunlight, the water column stabilizes. (Note that there is an important exception; when temperatures are in the range 0-4°C, colder water is less dense, hence ice floats.) The microscopic plankton, generally, cannot penetrate through the thermocline, so they become trapped often at increasingly concentrated biomass levels in warm surface waters.
- **Most organisms need O₂ to support their growth; they die if levels go too low.** Temperature affects the solubility of oxygen (O₂) in water; the higher the temperature, the less O₂ can be dissolved. As water is warmed, if the solubility of O₂ decreases below the current concentration, O₂ degasses out and escapes into the atmosphere. O₂ enters the water from the atmosphere and is also produced as a byproduct from photosynthesis. Most photosynthesis in water is performed by microalgae.
- **Temperature affects the rates of chemical reactions.** For organisms, those chemical reactions are controlled by proteins that they produce, called enzymes. As a generalization, and within limits, an increase in temperature by 10°C doubles an enzymatic reaction. In theory, then, if the water temperature was increased by 10°C, the plankton would grow twice as fast. In reality though, that relationship is narrow and as temperatures increase further proteins denature and organisms die.

Learning outcomes from operating the model

- Increasing nutrient loads increase the likelihood of extreme oscillations in the biomass of microalgae and zooplankton.
- Increased temperature exacerbates the likelihood of those oscillations.
- Differences in the temperature-growth relationship between the microalgae and zooplankton impact the dynamics of the food web.
- Combinations of high temperature (increasing rates of biological processes, such as growth) and low wind speed (minimising oxygen exchange with the atmosphere), together with an eutrophication event (pulse of nutrients), can be conducive to (increase the likelihood of) a hypoxic event.
- Whether the hypoxia develops is also affected by the timing of the temperature, wind and pollution events relative to the ecological state. For hypoxia to be most likely, the timings need to align with a developing microalgal population and with a low zooplankton population – this provides the greatest opportunity for the maximum biomass to accumulate, the death and decay of which draws down the oxygen concentration.

Modifications to the model

Here we consider just a few ways in which the model could be usefully modified:

- **Provide light in a day-night cycle** – currently the model describes a system that is not light-limited. Apart from the development of light-limitation in the microalgal populations due to self-shading at high biomass levels, the absence of a day-night cycle prevents the simulation of the contribution of respiration (i.e., the consumption of O_2) by the microalgae during night. This prevents a consideration of the direct impact of the microalgae in contributing to hypoxia as only their contribution to O_2 production is considered.
- **Provide a means to introduce organic pollution** – eutrophication is simulated here through providing a pulse of inorganic nutrient that directly supports microalgal growth via phototrophy which produces O_2 . In reality, eutrophication is typically associated also with the addition of organic pollution which loads the water with forms of POM and also dissolved organic matter (DOM). If this addition is made then the bacterial processing of that material would introduce an additional contribution to the BOD, decreasing the O_2 level. Furthermore, that decrease would occur before the recycled nutrients became available to support the growth of microalgae that would produce O_2 and help alleviate hypoxia.
- **Describe the physiology of the plankton in more detail** – specifically it would be useful to describe variable stoichiometry, i.e., changes in the C:N ratio so that these changes are simulated during continued microalgal growth after nutrient exhaustion. This would have various impacts on the simulation including a continuing production of biomass but also of a deteriorating food quality for the zooplankton. While more O_2 would be produced, most would be lost relative to the increasing amount of organics in the system. The absence of variable stoichiometry in the plankton model thus leads to an underestimation of the risk of hypoxia.
- **Describe the plankton community in more detail** – this would include adding other organism types, with different temperature-growth relationships, different growth rates, different nutritional values as prey items etc. This would greatly enhance the potential realism of the simulation, though inevitably (just as in reality) it would make the system more complex.
- **Include seasonality** – currently, other than changing temperature, the model takes no account of seasonality such as changing light levels, or of changes in the water column depth. These factors play a critical role in affecting microalgal growth, and thence the whole dynamics of the food web, in nature.

Consolidation of what you have learnt and further aspects

CLASS ACTIVITY #4

Having explored the concepts described in the model, consider how you think changes in temperature may affect the functioning of food webs that run from photosynthetic plankton through to fish.

You may wish to revisit your conclusions from Class Activities #1, #2, #3.

If you get stuck, you may wish to consider some of the issues expanded on below.

Temperature effects – some more details

Types of organism activity

There are two types of chemical reaction that drive the growth of organisms: **phototrophy**, which uses photosynthesis to build biomass from carbon dioxide (CO₂), and **heterotrophy**, which consumes biomass and chemicals that originated from photosynthesis, converting that material into new biomass with a connected loss of material (nutrient release and defecation) and energy. Phototrophy produces oxygen (O₂); heterotrophy consumes O₂.

The producers are photosynthetic, while all the other organism types are consumers.

While animals and bacteria are solely heterotrophic, phototrophs such as the planktonic microalgae also operate heterotrophic reactions. In the light, the phototrophic activity is greater than the heterotrophic activities; in consequence there is more O₂ produced than is consumed. In darkness, however, phototrophy cannot occur so only heterotrophic reactions are being performed by these microalgae; in the dark, these organisms are solely heterotrophic, and they consume O₂.

There are some microalgae species that also eat; these are called *mixoplankton*. Mixoplankton combine being a producer (fixing CO₂ and releasing O₂) and a consumer (releasing CO₂ and consuming O₂). These organisms can be important in certain ecosystems, and especially in summer waters. You may wish to consider how they might possibly react to temperature changes and to the risks of hypoxia in the water where they grow.

Optimal temperature for growth

Organisms evolve through natural selection as they grow within a given environment. Temperature is an important factor. Every organism has an optimal temperature for growth. If the temperature is too high relative to this optimum, death can rapidly follow. Conversely, if the temperature is too low, then the growth rate may not be competitive, or it may be lethal. This means that every organism grows within a temperature range (**Fig.3**). You can explore these interactions in the model.

Within that temperature range, success of an organism depends on how well adapted are the other organisms with which it competes, predated and otherwise interacts.

With climate change two events are occurring in this context:

1) Changes are occurring to the geographic distributions of temperature ranges which affect the potential zonation of organisms.

This is, in general terms, shifting the ranges of organisms polewards. Polar species are being squeezed out, and something of a 'species vacuum' is being created at low latitudes (i.e. near the equator) where the higher temperatures can only be exploited by relatively few species. However, for marine plankton, because of the geological structural differences of the seabed and the continent edges, moving to a different geographic location also changes the physical factors affecting ecology, such as water currents bringing in nutrients and different temperature regimes. Furthermore, moving an ecosystem also has a seasonal impact as the sunlight patterns change. Coupled with the physical changes (that affect mixed layer depths and nutrient supply etc.), this can lead to profound changes in the growth of microalgae. Events in ponds and lakes are obviously very different in this context to those in the ocean; organisms cannot shift to different locations as they may within the ocean, though transfers of plankton between lakes occur due to animal vectors (notably, wading birds).

2) The rate of change in temperature is affecting evolution.

While in theory, species can adapt and thus remain growing in its current geographic location, temperature changes may occur too rapidly so that adaptation cannot keep up. In addition, the magnitude of the changes in temperature can be such that organisms can proliferate beyond ecological control because their competitors and/or predators cannot grow well at the elevated temperatures. Organisms also evolve at different rates, so unforeseen changes can occur to the ecology in a given location.

Light-dark interactions

What of the photosynthetic organisms that may be expected to introduce O₂ into the water column? Photosynthesis may be considered as two processes:

- the 'light-reactions' that convert light energy into chemical energy and split water to generate O₂; the more light, the more chemical energy that can be generated.
- the so-called 'dark-reactions' that use that chemical energy from the light-reactions, to make sugars and thence fuel growth of the photosynthetic organism. The dark-reactions are not really isolated to darkness; they just do not have a direct requirement for light.

While these reactions are coupled in photosynthesis, the light-reaction is relatively insensitive to temperature, but the dark-reactions are as sensitive to temperature as are other enzymatic processes in organisms.

Now, consider what happens in a warm sunny environment, with temperature ranges that are within the optimum range for growth. The high sunlight levels support good light-reaction rates, supporting good O₂ release and also high CO₂-fixation rates, the latter enhanced by increased temperatures. This extra biomass growth in turn supports the growth of non-photosynthetic (i.e., heterotrophic) organisms via food web interactions. The released O₂ saturates the water column, supporting the activities of those heterotrophic organisms. However, various factors are also developing that combine to lead to potentially dangerous conditions:

- During the day, if O₂ levels rise above the saturation level for a given water temperature and salinity, there will be an outgassing, perhaps so fast that O₂ bubbles are visible, such that the stoichiometry of organic-C : O₂ is disturbed. Such conditions increase the potential BOD above that which can be satisfied readily by the O₂ concentrations.
- At night, the photosynthetic organisms themselves consume O₂. This night-time respiration contributes to the day-night oscillation cycle of O₂ concentration; up in the light, down in darkness. Furthermore, the greater the accumulating phototrophic biomass, the greater that oscillation; remember that the maximum level of O₂ during the day is capped by the saturation threshold at the water temperature (that threshold becoming lower as temperatures increase), while at the lower end, life for organisms needing O₂ will ultimately halt as O₂ levels are drained down below the hypoxic level of 2g O₂ m⁻³.
- The more nutrient in the water (contributing to 'eutrophication'), the greater the accumulating biomass of phototrophs. That increasing biomass can also lead to a higher biomass of other organisms, most obviously of those that feed on the phototrophs or on organics that accumulate such as mucus and faecal material.
- The increased phototrophic biomass makes the water turn increasingly green-brown in colour. This starts to limit light availability for each organism through a process called self-shading. This limits the production of O₂ during the day, while the increasingly high biomass of both the phototrophs and of all other members of the food web increases the drain of O₂ at night.
- If the weather breaks, such that there is increased cloud cover and the day light level decreases, then the level of photosynthesis that would top up the O₂ content of the water during the daytime will be less. However, water cools slowly, so the night-time respiration rates that consume O₂ will remain as they were; the collective consumption of O₂ could then draw it down to dangerous levels. Cloudy nights also lead to slower heat loss from the water surface, exacerbating the situation, especially if wind speeds remain low.

If the phototrophic organisms are also predators, that is they are mixoplankton, then the situation can become more complicated again. These organisms can have a higher respiration rate at night, and if their day-time photosynthesis is decreased (due to a change in the weather) then they could increase their heterotrophic activity further. If the mixoplankton are toxic, they may also kill other organisms, including other phototrophs, while the growth of heterotrophs (notably bacteria) on the debris from predation would also increase. The net result of all these events would be to increase the potential for deoxygenation to occur down to dangerous levels.

Temperature and oxygen

Temperature affects the oxygen (O₂) content of water. The higher the temperature, the less gas can be held in the water. For O₂-requiring aquatic organisms, including fish and almost all other animals, as well as most of the plankton that support the aquatic food webs, this temperature linkage to the challenge of life at a low O₂ content is coupled also to the effect of temperature on metabolic rates. As temperature increases, so metabolic rates increase, requiring more O₂ to be extracted from the water, but that water itself (even at saturation) contains less O₂.

Collectively, for rapidly growing populations of organisms, the abovementioned activities can all rapidly lead to de-oxygenation of the water column and death. Death itself provides much organic

material supporting the growth of bacteria, which draw down the O₂ levels even further, while growth of anaerobic bacteria produces chemicals that are themselves also harmful to O₂-needing organisms.

Water column stability

The stabilization of the water cuts off the warmer surface waters from the colder deeper waters at a depth called the **thermocline**. The thermocline forms through a process called **stratification**. Stratification is also affected by wind, such that a combination of increasing temperatures and decreasing wind strength during the transition of weather from winter to summer decreases the depth of the thermocline. The depth of the water from the surface to the thermocline is termed the '**mixed layer depth**' (**MLD**); water above the MLD, up to the surface, separates organisms and nutrients from those below. Plankton, generally, cannot penetrate through the thermocline, so they become trapped often at increasingly concentrated biomass levels in surface waters. Some plankton, however, can migrate down to the MLD, usually at night, to collect nutrients or they (zooplankton) swim up at night to feed.

In situations where freshwater meets seawater, such as near coastal barrages, the freshwater can form a layer floating on top of the seawater. In such conditions, the seawater is cut off from the atmosphere and decaying material from the freshwater sinks into the seawater zone. Here the decay depletes O₂ and the whole salt-water zone may become hypoxic. In such systems, air may be artificially pumped into the seawater zone to help prevent hypoxia from developing.

Water column stability and the balance of oxygen production and its use by microalgae

In the upper mixed water column, above the thermocline, there is a gradient of light. At the top there is enough (perhaps more than enough – it can be inhibitory) light to support photosynthesis, while at the bottom light will be increasingly limiting. Across such a light gradient, a balance point can be identified when there is just enough light to support a rate of phototrophy in microalgae (producing O₂) that equals their heterotrophy (using O₂). That balance point is the **compensation point**; for microalgae growing in a water column, the depth that this occurs at is the **critical depth**. The location of the critical depth varies with surface day light and hence will change with the seasons and also very rapidly as the weather changes and clouds cross the sky. Furthermore, as the microalgae population grows, and the water colour becomes increasingly green-brown, the organisms themselves absorb light and the population self-shades itself. For a given amount of surface light, this self-shading will bring the critical depth closer to the surface.

Temperature is involved in these events as it is a function of seasonality and the weather, it affects the mixed layer depth, and it affects the growth rate of the planktonic microalgae which in turn affects the relative rates of phototrophy and heterotrophy as the critical depth changes.

Nutrient availability; the role of eutrophication

As you will have seen from using the model, eutrophication either as a background elevated nutrient level or (and especially) as a nutrient pulse, greatly increases the risk of hypoxia. That is more so if the event occurs in conjunction with elevated temperatures as that promotes more rapid plankton

growth while decreasing O₂ solubility. Under climate change, we are seeing increased incidents of flash flooding which overloads the terrestrial ecosystem (and sewage systems) resulting in flows of nutrients into lakes and coastal areas. Although the water flow may temporarily dilute the plankton, the extra nutrient added to the system promotes more biomass development. Sooner or later the plankton using the added nutrient will likely exhaust one of the major nutrients (N or P), leading to changes in the biomass stoichiometry and thence in the operation of the food web.

Summary of temperature effects

As we have seen, there are direct and indirect impacts of temperature on plankton ecology. While, on first consideration, an increase in the growth of O₂-producing organisms runs counter to hypoxia-causing eutrophication, actually the proliferation of microalgae in conditions of eutrophication plus elevated temperatures may present a severe risk to aquatic ecosystems. The control of eutrophication becomes more important as temperatures increase under climate change.

These interactions, as considered in detail above, are summarized in **Fig.7**.

The impacts of these effects on other components of the aquatic ecosystem include:

- Changes in food abundance for other organisms – as different members of the plankton will have different temperature-growth relationships (e.g., see **Fig.3**), so the plankton community composition will alter. At the extreme, where most organisms die due to a lack of oxygen, the bacterial community (including anaerobes) will benefit.
- Changes in the availability of oxygen to support the activity of other organisms – the balance of phototrophy and heterotrophy, together with factors that affect gas exchange and oxygen solubility, will affect the availability of oxygen for higher trophic levels, through to fish. At the other extreme, very low levels of oxygen will enable the growth of facultative and then (at zero O₂) obligatory anaerobic bacteria.

As detailed above, the likelihood of different consequences depends on the rapidity of changes in temperature (and of light) and also on the levels of nutrients available in the system.

Fig.7 Direct and indirect interactions between temperature and plankton activity. Increased day light and more general increases in temperature with climate change leads to a temperature rise in the water (i). This temperature increase is enhanced under calm conditions (ii), while both warmer and calmer conditions also lead to a shallower mixed layer depth (MLD; iii). A shallow MLD keeps the photosynthetic microalgae nearer the light, promoting their growth (i.e., a deep MLD negatively affects microalgal growth (iv). Increased temperature, but not calm conditions, enhances gas exchange with the atmosphere (v), which operates to equilibrate the levels of oxygen (vi), while increased temperature itself decreases oxygen solubility (vii). Phototrophic growth is enhanced by day light and elevated temperature (viii), assuming otherwise good conditions for the microalgae. Elevated nutrient levels, especially associated with eutrophication, promotes microalgal growth (ix), noting that nutrients are recycled from heterotrophic (including predator) activity. At extreme microalgal abundances, the resultant self-shading leads to surface accumulations of the biomass, darkening the water below while excess O₂ production is rapidly outgassed to the atmosphere. Phototrophic growth increases oxygen levels, but at night the heterotrophic (respiratory) activities of these organisms, as well as all other organisms, consumes oxygen (x). The growth of phototrophs promotes the growth of heterotrophic organisms (xi); growth of the latter is also promoted by elevated temperatures (xii). Heterotrophs consume oxygen; if oxygen levels become sufficiently depressed, aerobic heterotrophic growth is negatively impacted (xiii) as the system becomes hypoxic.

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